

TEACHING GRAMMAR THROUGH TEXTS FOR A2 LEVEL

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Abstract: This article is adapted for A2 level students studying English grammar. The article contains information on improving the pronunciation of students with A2 level, working with class texts to improve the level in the room, and what A2 level is like.

Key words: technically, beginner level, Authentic texts, classroom texts, pronunciation, Framework Pre-intermediate A2

English level A2 is the second level of English in the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR), a definition of different language levels written by the Council of Europe. In everyday speech, this level might be described as “basic” as in “I speak basic English”. Although A2 is technically still “beginner level”, you will have to cover serious ground to reach it.

A2 Levels are generally harder than AS Levels. They build on the knowledge you learn taking your AS papers. Many A2 Level papers also test on the content covered in the AS papers. For example, business studies A2 exams require you to recall knowledge from AS business studies.

Find a range of lesson plans to use with teenage learners at pre-intermediate level. All of our lessons are designed around themes that are engaging and relevant to secondary learners and can be used to complement your school curriculum, giving students an opportunity to develop their English language and skills in motivating and enjoyable ways. Written by young learner experts from around the world, our lesson plans are easy to use and aim to give your students the skills and confidence they need to enjoy learning English.

This is Mr West. He has a bag in his left hand. Where is he standing? He is standing at the door of his house. What is Mr West going to do? He is going to put his hand into his pocket. He is going to take a key out of his pocket. He is going to put the key into the lock. (from Hornby, A.S. Oxford Progressive English Course, Oxford University Press, 1954)

Authentic texts or classroom texts?

Advocates of authentic texts argue that not only are such specially written EFL texts uninteresting - and therefore unmotivating - but they misrepresent the way the language is used in real-life contexts. On the other hand, the problems associated with authentic texts cannot be wished away, either, as any teacher who has attempted to use a dense newspaper article with low level students will

have discovered. The linguistic load of unfamiliar vocabulary and syntactic complexity can make such texts impenetrable, and ultimately very demotivating.

Advantages of using texts:

- o They provide co-textual information, allowing learners to deduce the meaning of unfamiliar grammatical items from the co-text.
- o If the texts are authentic they can show how the item is used in real communication.

Stairway to nowhere (lower level)

Stairway to nowhere is a complete set of teaching resources designed around an interesting and unusual photograph with activities to activate your students' higher level critical thinking skills. This pack looks at the topics of day trips and unexplained sights. The focus is on developing students' reading skills and listening for specific information.

What tenses do A2 students know?

Course Info

Present simple.

Past simple.

Present continuous.

Future.

Key verbs.

Tense review.

Younger Learners: A2 English Tenses

Are you studying for Cambridge A2 Key for Schools? Do you need to be more confident with English tenses? This short course covers key tenses you need at this level. The lessons are fun, interactive and designed to give you lots of practice!

What is my A2 level student able to do?

According to the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR), students are starting to understand language and how it functions on a social level. The CEFR explains and classifies language skills on an international standard. A2 level students have a simple understanding of communication and are able to use everyday English from:

Understanding sentences/questions that is related to him/her (family, what he/she likes, etc).

Greetings: They can introduce themselves confidently

Telling you how they are feeling and asking how you are feeling

Reacting to questions or statements made

Ask and answer questions

Talking about what they have done during the day

Ask for basic information

Keeping this in mind, let's take a look at the top 3 tips for teaching A2 level students.

Keep it simple

Keeping in mind that A2 levelled students are still beginners, but at this point, they have been exposed to English, so it is very important to keep your language, instructions and questions as simple as possible. In other words, you need to ensure you speak slowly and keep incidental language to a minimum, as you don't want to confuse your students. Always keep your sentences short, simple and remember, REPETITION is key. With that in mind, drilling is as important as drinking water. When introducing a new language, you need to ensure you are reinforcing the concept of drilling, as it will help your learners with:

Pronunciation

Retention

The first part is known as the Advanced Subsidiary level (AS level). The second part is known as the A2 level. The AS Level is a qualification in its own right, and the AS Level together with the A2 Level forms the complete A Level qualification.

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